

Simulating Hyperelastic Materials with Anisotropic Stiffness Models in a Particle-Based Framework

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Figure 1: This paper presents a particle-based anisotropic elastic simulation approach utilizing the smoothed particle hydrodynamics method. This figure illustrates the simulation of muscle contraction (indicated by the red area) in a snake using our proposed method. The snake effectively slithers across the ground.

Abstract

We present a particle-based smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) framework for simulating hyperelastic materials with anisotropic stiffness models. While most elastic simulations predominantly rely on mesh-based approaches, such as the Finite Element method, the relationship between Lamé’s first parameter and Poisson’s ratio complicates the strict enforcement of volume conservation, making it challenging to stabilize simulations for common biological tissues like fat and muscle. In this paper, we couple an implicit divergence-free SPH solver with particle-based deformation gradient computation and apply various elastic energy functions to achieve incompressible elastic simulations. The incompressibility of

elastic objects and collisions between different bodies are managed by the implicit SPH algorithm. We further incorporate anisotropic energy functions, constructed from the extrapolation of Cauchy-Green invariants, to introduce anisotropic properties to the objects. By integrating activation and contraction coefficients into the energy functions, particles can simulate muscle contractions and lift heavy objects. Our method can effectively represent elastic objects with varying mechanical properties across different directions and be further employed to mimic muscle contractions. Experiments demonstrate that our approach provides realistic simulations for a wide range of animal and human body movements.

Keywords: physically-based animation, particle systems, elastic simulation, smoothed particle hydrodynamics

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Figure 2: SPH framework for simulating hyperelastic materials with anisotropic stiffness model.

1 Introduction

The simulation of hyperelastic materials is of paramount importance in the field of computer graphics, with applications spanning various domains such as virtual surgery[38], soft robotics[23], and the study of biological tissues[4]. Over the years, numerous discretization methods have been utilized to study these materials, with mesh-based techniques such as the Finite Element method (FEM) dominating the research landscape[32]. FEM has been favored due to its accuracy, ability to handle complex geometries, and compatibility with a wide range of material models. However, in recent years, particle-based methods like Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) have garnered increasing attention as an alternative to mesh-based techniques[29]. This growing interest is attributed to several factors, including the versatility of SPH in handling a diverse range of material properties, its ease of coupling with other simulation techniques, and the inherent guarantees of incompressibility it provides[19]. Additionally, particle-based methods offer unique advantages in terms of computational efficiency and scalability, making them well-suited for complex applications and large-scale simulations[20].

Particle-based methods offer several advantages compared to their mesh-based counterparts. Among these benefits are the ability to handle large deformations and topology changes more naturally, the absence of mesh distortion and element inversion issues, and the potential for efficient parallelization. Thanks to the study of simulating incompressible fluid using

particles, SPH now can be applied to handle strongly incompressible elastic objects with existing elastic energy functions. And since each particle carries a certain portion of mass of the whole object, the Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor of the energy models can be directly applied to computing the motion of the objects without the need of the Hessian matrices[5]. Consequently, numerous successful particle-based elastic simulation research endeavors have emerged.

Despite these advancements, there is a noticeable lack of anisotropic elastic simulation studies in particle-based methods. Anisotropic materials exhibit different mechanical properties depending on the direction in which they are measured, as opposed to isotropic materials, which have uniform properties in all directions[17]. This anisotropic behavior is commonly observed in various materials encountered in daily life, such as wood, which exhibits varying stiffness along and perpendicular to the grain, and composite materials like carbon fiber, where the arrangement of fibers influences the mechanical properties. Anisotropic materials are also found in biological tissues, such as muscles, tendons, and cartilage, which possess distinct stiffness characteristics along their primary axes due to their underlying fibrous structures[25]. Accurate simulation of anisotropic materials is of paramount importance in computer graphics, as it enables the creation of more realistic and lifelike virtual environments, objects, and characters. This is especially relevant in applications like medical simulation, where accurate representation of biological tissues is essential for effective training and planning of surgical procedures, as well

as in the entertainment industry, where realistic animations contribute significantly to the overall visual experience. Given the prevalence of anisotropic materials in daily life and their significance in various applications, there is a pressing need to develop effective particle-based methods for anisotropic elastic simulation. By addressing this gap in the research landscape, we can pave the way for more accurate and realistic simulations of a wide range of materials and objects, ultimately enhancing the fidelity and practicality of computer graphics applications in various domains.

In this paper, we introduce a particle-based SPH framework for simulating hyperelastic materials with anisotropic stiffness models. As is shown in Figure 2, we couple an implicit divergence-free SPH solver with particle-based deformation gradient computation and apply various elastic energy functions to achieve incompressible elastic simulations. The incompressibility of elastic objects and collisions between different bodies are also managed by the implicit SPH algorithm[37]. To incorporate anisotropic properties, we integrate anisotropic energy functions constructed from the extrapolation of Cauchy-Green invariants[18]. By integrating activation and contraction coefficients into the energy functions, particles can simulate muscle contractions and lift heavy objects. Our method effectively represents elastic objects with varying mechanical properties across different directions and can be further employed to mimic muscle contractions.

In conclusion, this work presents a novel approach to simulating hyperelastic materials with anisotropic stiffness models using a particle-based SPH framework. Our method addresses the current gap in anisotropic elastic simulation studies for particle-based techniques and offers a more robust and versatile solution compared to traditional mesh-based methods. Positioned within the broader research landscape, this work contributes to the ongoing development of more accurate, efficient, and adaptable simulation methods for hyperelastic materials. Through a series of experiments, we demonstrate that our approach can provide realistic simulations for a wide range of animal and human body movements, underscoring its potential for diverse applications in computer graph-

ics, biomechanics, and material science.

2 Related work

The simulation of deformable objects with physics-based models has a long history in computer graphics. A vast range of methods have been proposed to achieve a detailed and realistic effect of deformable objects. The early research on deformable objects is introduced in Nealen[28] work.

Particle-based methods: Among these typical methods, the Mass-spring system is a simple and early particle-based approach to implement for simulating deformable materials. As a result, Mass-spring systems are widely used for a range of deformable objects, like cloth simulation[8], geometrically complex deformable solids[36] and hair[31]. Liu et al.[24] subsequently proposed a new implicit Euler numerical method for dynamics of mass-spring systems, which has been applied to simulate the motion of cloth pieces, wiring harnesses, bulk objects, and character clothing.

Though the above mentioned methods are easy to implement, explaining the physics-based simulation of deformable bodies remains a significant challenge. The deformation gradient in physics formulation is difficult to incorporate into the Mass-spring systems, while some other particle-based methods could resolve these problems. One of the most compelling approaches is the SPH methods which are well known for their behavior of simulating fluid[6][7] and fluid-rigid interaction[1]. Its Lagrangian property allows the displacement field and gradient deformation to be easily evaluated by exploiting the gradient of the smoothing kernel, which is quite attractive to the simulation of deformable objects. Desbrun and Gascuel[26] first introduced the SPH methods into the simulation of inelastic deformable objects and viscous fluids. However, a key problem is that the standard SPH kernel gradient evaluation is not first-order consistent, which means that the rotation of the deformation couldn't be captured. Müller et al.[27] proposed a particle-based approach to simulate a wide range of elastically and plastically deformable objects which can

melt, flow, solidify split and merge. They used the Moving Least Squares (MLS) procedure to compute the spatial derivatives of the discrete displacement field to obtain strain and stress. Becker et al.[5] introduced a novel corotated SPH formulation for deformable elastic solids that solves the missing rotational invariance of previous approaches and is capable of calculating elastic forces for a wide range of scenes using the linear Cauchy-Green tensor. However, their method only considers the elastic deformation, Zhou et al.[40] presented a novel particle-based method for simulating elastoplastic materials with implicit numerical integration on a sparse linear system, allowing for a wider range of stiffness and plasticity settings.

In recent years, several studies have explored smoothed-particle hydrodynamics (SPH) methods for simulating elastic objects due to their ability to provide a unified framework for simulating different materials, such as rigid bodies and fluid mixtures. Peer et al.[29] focused on the rotation of the linear infinitesimal strain tensor and used a correction matrix to ensure the first-order consistency of the kernel gradient and capture a rotation extraction directly from the SPH deformation gradient. They proposed implicit formulation and adapted rotation estimation that enables significantly larger time steps and higher stiffness for the simulation of deformable objects. Building on this work, Gissler et al.[11] fixed the wrong velocity of the elastic objects during the iteration in Akinci[1] approach, and corrected the pressure between fluid and solid. They introduced Peer[29] method of elastic methods to realize the bidirectional coupling between fluid and deformable solid. Gissler et al.[10] subsequently proposed an elastoplastic SPH approach for snow that combines two implicit solvers guided by Peer[29] work and simulated various snow effects such as snow fall and accumulation, deformation, breaking, compression and hardening. Kugelstadt et al.[22] introduced a new SPH operator splitting formulation of the corotated linear elastic material model, which enables faster time-stepping than the state-of-the-art method by Peer[29].

FEM/Mesh methods: In addition to the aforementioned particle-based methods, the Finite Element Method (FEM) is another attractive approach for simulating elastic objects, as it can compute an explicit deformation function and enable the reversal of deformations with precision. The theory of FEM simulation of deformable solids has been introduced in Sifakis[32] work. However, the deformation function becomes ill-conditioned when there is a significant plastic flow (permanent deformation), leading to numerical instability in the simulation. Bargteil et al.[3] presented extensions to standard finite element methods that allow for simulating large plastic flow in solid materials. Kharevych et al.[15] used homogenization theory to allow for the approximation of a deformable object made of arbitrary fine structures of various linear elastic materials with a dynamically similar coarse model. To simulate volumetric deformable bodies with nonlinear rest shape, Bargteil et al.[2] developed a quadratic tetrahedral element based on the Bézier basis for graphical animation of deformable bodies. In [39], Xu et al. presented a new method with the gradient of SVD for simulating nonlinear materials using the principal stretches of the material and applied this method to isotropic and anisotropic material design for soft-body simulation in computer animation. Afterwards, Smith et al. [33] extended a new Neo-Hookean elasticity model that maintains the fleshy appearance of the Neo-Hookean model and exhibits superior volume preservation. Kugelstadt et al.[21] presented a new method based on a volumetric approach using tetrahedral elements to represent the shape of the object, which allows for more accurate and realistic simulation and simulated the complex deformation of soft objects without introducing numerical artifacts in real-time using corotated finite elements. Smith et al.[34] resolved Hessian indefiniteness by investigating eigenstructures analytically and presented closed-form expressions for the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of all tensor invariant. Kim et al.[16] used the finite element method with a new formulation of the Baraff-Witkin cloth model. This model is shown to be a coupled anisotropic strain energy, with a stretching term that approximates the isotropic As-Rigid-As-Possible (ARAP) energy.

MPM methods: In recent years, the Material Point Method (MPM) has become a popular approach for multi-material simulation due to its advantages over both particles and meshes. Stomakhin et al.[35] first introduced this method to simulate snow and some phase changes of snow as elastoplastic materials. Afterwards, Jiang et al.[14] resolved the large dissipation or instabilities during the transfer between the particles and meshes by augmenting each particle with a locally affine description of the velocity. In [12], Hu et al. extended their ideas and used MLS to replace the shape functions in the stress divergence term. This enables the simulation of various new phenomena and results in a double speed up and easier implementation. Daviet and Bertails-Descoubes[9] developed a model for granular materials that behave like solids due to internal friction. They represented granular matter as a compressible viscoplastic fluid combined with a Drucker-Prager yield criterion and a unilateral compressibility constraint. In [13], Jiang et al. designed anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive models to characterize the response of manifold strain and shear and also proposed a new elastoplastic constitutive model defining the collision response, which could process collision-intensive scenes with millions of degrees of freedom in just a few minutes per frame. However, the anisotropic energies are not inversion-safe and contained spurious stable states under large deformation. To address this issue, Kim et al.[17] proposed a robust, inversion-safe anisotropic model called the Anisotropic ARAP energy. They presented a rehabilitation approach that allows badly-conditioned elements to be simulated robustly and efficiently. They used MPM methods to implement the behavior of anisotropic hyperelasticity, specifically transverse isotropy. In [30], Schreck and Wojtan built a generalized model of anisotropy that can be integrated into current MPM elastoplasticity solvers and an orthotropic law reducing the complexity of the generalized model, which provides a more efficient and effective simulation of anisotropic materials.

In conclusion, the above methods have provided comprehensive insight into isotropic elastoplastic solids. However, for anisotropic elastic objects, recent relevant research has primarily adopted meshed-based FEM and MPM

methods. This paper introduces the particle-based method to simulate anisotropic elastic materials, combining the SPH method framework with the anisotropic energy function to achieve the simulation of hyperelastic materials with anisotropic stiffness models.

3 Deformation gradient in SPH and energy functions

3.1 Computation of physical values using SPH approach

In the SPH method, the continuum is discretized into a set of particles, each representing a volume element of the fluid. The physical properties of the fluid, such as density, pressure, and velocity, are then calculated by approximating the values at each particle based on the values of neighboring particles.

One of the key equations used in SPH is the approximation of a physical quantity A at a particle i , which can be expressed as:

$$A(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_j A(\mathbf{x}_j) V_j W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j are the positions of particles i and j , respectively, V_j is the volume associated with particle j , h is the smoothing length used to define the influence radius of a particle, and W is the smoothing kernel function that assigns weights to neighboring particles based on their distance from the current particle. Equation 1 essentially states that the value of A at particle i is a sum of the values of A at all neighboring particles j , weighted by their volumes and the smoothing kernel function. This approach allows for a continuous approximation of physical properties across the fluid, and has been shown to be effective in simulating a wide range of fluid phenomena.

To extrapolate this idea, the gradient of A can be computed using the same approach as Equation 1. The gradient of A at a particle i can be approximated as:

$$\nabla A_i = \sum_j A_j V_j \nabla_i W_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

where A_i , A_j is the abbreviation of $A(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and $A(\mathbf{x}_j)$. $\nabla_i W$ is the gradient of the smoothing

Linear elasticity	$\Psi_{\text{LE}} = \mu \ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_l\ _F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}^2(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_l)$ $\mathbf{P}_{\text{LE}}(\mathbf{F}) = 2\mu\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_l + \lambda \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_l) \mathbf{I}$
Co-rotated linear elasticity	$\Psi_{\text{CR}} = \mu \ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c\ _F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c)$ $\mathbf{P}_{\text{CR}}(\mathbf{F}) = \mathbf{R} [2\mu\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c + \lambda \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c) \mathbf{I}]$
St. Venant-Kirchhoff elasticity	$\Psi_{\text{StVK}} = \mu \ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_G\ _F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}^2(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_G)$ $\mathbf{P}_{\text{StVK}}(\mathbf{F}) = \mathbf{F} [2\mu\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_G + \lambda \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_G) \mathbf{I}]$
Neo-Hookean elasticity	$\Psi_{\text{Neo}} = \frac{\mu}{2} \left(\ \mathbf{F}\ _F^2 - 3 \right) - \mu \log(J) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \log^2(J)$ $\mathbf{P}_{\text{Neo}}(\mathbf{F}) = \mu (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{F}^{-T}) + \lambda \log(J) \mathbf{F}^{-T}$

Table 1: Energy functions

kernel function with respect to the position of particle i . And W_{ij} is the short form of $W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h)$. To further reduce the higher order error, we can use the property of $\nabla 1 = \mathbf{0}$ and modify Equation 2 to $\nabla A(\mathbf{x}_i) - A(\mathbf{x}_i) \nabla 1$ to get:

$$\nabla A_i = \sum_j A_{ji} V_j \nabla_i W_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

where A_{ji} represents $A_j - A_i$. In the following we will use Equation 3 for all SPH gradient-related computation.

3.2 Deformation gradient

The deformation gradient is a tensor that characterizes the deformation of a material. In the context of continuum mechanics, it serves as a mean to relate the deformed state of a material to its undeformed state. Mathematically, the deformation gradient, denoted as \mathbf{F} , is a second-order tensor defined as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{x}}}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{x} represents the current position of a particle in the deformed state, and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ corresponds to its initial position in the undeformed state. The deformation gradient \mathbf{F} encapsulates the local stretching, compression, and rotation of the material at each point within the domain.

In order to compute the deformation gradient using the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method, we can employ an approach analogous to Equation 3. In this case, the physical value A corresponds to the particles' positions in the deformed state, while the relative po-

sitions between them are equivalent to the initial positions. Consequently, we arrive at:

$$\mathbf{F}_i = \sum_j \mathbf{x}_{ji} V_j \otimes \nabla_i W_{ij}, \quad (5)$$

where \otimes denotes the outer product, and $\nabla_i W_{ij}$ represents $W(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_j, h)$. However, similar to the preference for using Equation 3 over Equation 2 for computing gradients, computational errors may arise when directly applying Equation 5 to calculate the deformation gradient near object boundaries. Owing to the absence of neighboring particles, the condition $\mathbf{F}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i) = \sum_j (\bar{\mathbf{x}}_j - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i) V_j \otimes \nabla_i W_{ij} = \mathbf{I}$, with \mathbf{I} as the identity matrix, may not hold for undeformed positions. To rectify this error, we can add $\mathbf{F}^{-1}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i)$ to $\nabla_i W_{ij}$ in Equation 5 as a weight matrix.

The deformation gradient tensor, \mathbf{F} , can be utilized to compute the strain tensor, which quantifies the extent to which a material has been deformed. Subsequently, the strain tensor can be employed to calculate stress, which measures the forces exerted on the material.

Infinitesimal strain	$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_l = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{F} + \mathbf{F}^T) - \mathbf{I}$
Co-rotated strain	$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c = \mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}$
Green strain	$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_G = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{I})$

Table 2: Tensor notations

3.3 Energy functions

In the study of hyperelastic materials, energy functions play a crucial role in relating the defor-

mation of a material to the forces acting upon it. An energy function, typically denoted as Ψ , represents the strain energy density of a material. It is a scalar function that quantifies the amount of energy stored in a material as a result of its deformation. This stored energy arises due to the internal resistance of the material to deformation and is dissipated when the material returns to its undeformed state.

The purpose of the energy function is to describe the material's mechanical behavior under various deformation states. The energy function depends on the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} and can be used to derive the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor (PK1) \mathbf{P} , which is related to the forces exerted on a material. The relationship between the energy function Ψ and the stress tensor \mathbf{P} is given by:

$$\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{F}) = \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{F}}, \quad (6)$$

Different energy functions can be designed and employed to model various material behaviors. For hyperelastic materials, the key factors for designing a successful energy function are to ensure the function can accurately capture the local material's stretches and compressions while remaining unaffected by its rotation and translation. Some of the classical energy functions and their first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensors are listed in Table 1. In these expressions, μ and λ represent Lamé's first and second parameters, respectively. The further related tensors used in these energy functions are shown in Table 2. From these tables, we can observe that Linear elasticity, Co-rotated linear elasticity, and St. Venant-Kirchhoff elasticity have similar forms, except for the strain tensors in them. In Table 2, $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}$ represents the Cauchy-Green Tensor, and \mathbf{S} is the stretching part of \mathbf{F} after the polar decomposition $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{S}$. Both ϵ_G and ϵ_c are immune to the rotation part in \mathbf{F} . The immunity to rotation is evident for ϵ_c with the \mathbf{R} part removed. For ϵ_G , we can perform singular value decomposition (SVD) on \mathbf{F} and find that $\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}^T \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}^2 \mathbf{V}^T$ contains only the square of the stretching. However, for Linear elasticity using the Infinitesimal strain, the rotation part cannot be efficiently eliminated during the computation. Special care must be taken in Equation 5 to

Figure 3: Elastic cuboid squashing experiments employing four different energy functions, with a Young's modulus of $E = 5 \times 10^4$ for all cases. The figure uses color-coding to represent the forces applied to the particles, with more intense colors indicating a higher degree of resistance.

produce a rotation-aware deformation gradient computation.

I_1	$\text{tr}(\mathbf{C}) = \sum_j \sigma_j^2$
I_2	$\text{tr}(\mathbf{C}^2) = \sum_j \sigma_j^4$
I_3	$\det(\mathbf{C}) = \det(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}) = \prod_j \sigma_x^2$
I_4^{ext}	$\mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{S} \mathbf{a} = \sum_j \tilde{a}_j^2 \sigma_j$
I_5^{ext}	$\mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} \mathbf{a} = \sum_j \tilde{a}_j^2 \sigma_j^2$

Table 3: The Cauchy-Green invariants (row 1-3) and their anisotropic extended forms (row 4-5).

The Neo-Hookean elasticity model stands out from the other three models due to its ability to preserve the size of objects in both linear and volumetric scales. This unique characteristic can be observed by examining the Cauchy-Green invariants in Table 3, where I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 are invariants that describe the deformation of an elastic element over time. In the table, σ denotes the singular values found in the matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, which results from the polar decomposition of \mathbf{F} , while j signifies the number of dimensions. I_1 and I_2 represent the quadratic and quartic combinations of all singular values, respectively. Both of these invariants return to 2 or 3 when an elastic object is neither compressed nor expanded in 2D or 3D

Figure 4: Elastic cuboid stretching experiments employ four different energy functions, with a Young’s modulus of $E = 5 \times 10^4$ for all cases. The figure uses color-coding to represent the forces applied on the particles, with more intense colors indicating a higher degree of resistance.

space. Conversely, I_3 calculates the product of all singular values, representing the area or volume of the elastic element.

By converting the energy functions in Table 1 into the form of Cauchy-Green invariants, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi_{\text{LE}} &= \mu \left(I_1 - 2\sqrt{I_1} - 3 \right) + \text{tr}^2(\epsilon_l) \\
 \Psi_{\text{CR}} &= \mu \left(I_1 - 2\sqrt{I_1} + 3 \right) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\sqrt{I_1} + 3 \right)^2 \\
 \Psi_{\text{StVK}} &= \frac{\mu}{4} (I_2 - 2I_1 + 3) + \frac{\lambda}{8} (I_1 - 3)^2 \\
 \Psi_{\text{Neo}} &= \frac{\mu}{2} (I_2 - 3) - \mu \log(I_3) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \log^2(I_3)
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

under 3D and we can see that not only Ψ_{LE} is not rotation-free, but also only Ψ_{Neo} contains I_3 to conserve the total volume.

In Figures 3 and 4, we designed two sets of experiments to evaluate the performance of various energy functions under squashing and stretching scenarios. The linear energy model employed in these experiments was further processed using the method described in [29] to remove rotation from the deformation gradient. An elastic cuboid was subjected to stretch-

ing and squashing in these experiments. The color transition from white to red represents the magnitude of the resistance force at each particle. Although the distribution of forces varies among the four energy models, they all maintain a similar deformation with a Poisson’s ratio of $\nu = 0.4$. In particular, the linear energy and co-rotated energy models exhibit nearly identical force distributions, as they preserve a similar combination of Cauchy-Green invariants. However, when the Poisson’s ratio increases to $\nu = 0.49$ to simulate a near-incompressible state, significant instability occurs for both the linear and co-rotated energy functions, and observable jitters appear in the StVK model during the stretching experiment, while the Neo-Hookean model remains stable. This can be attributed to the absence of the I_3 term in the former three models, which hinders their ability to efficiently preserve volumes.

3.4 Anisotropic invariants

To incorporate anisotropic stiffness into an object, we need to combine additional anisotropic energy with the traditional isotropic energy. First, we determine a direction for the anisotropic constraint, represented as a unit vector \mathbf{a} . Then, we ensure that the anisotropic energy responds only to deformations along \mathbf{a} and remains unaffected by deformations perpendicular to it. We achieve this by projecting the singular values of all dimensions onto the \mathbf{a} direction.

4 Anisotropic energy function

We follow the ideas from previous papers[25] and describe the stretching state of the elastic element with the matrix \mathbf{S} , obtained from the deformation gradient without rotation. The SVD of this rotation-free matrix is given by $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T$. To incorporate the direction vector \mathbf{a} into $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, we rotate \mathbf{a} into the stretching space by multiplying it with \mathbf{V}^T , resulting in $\tilde{\mathbf{a}} = \mathbf{V}^T\mathbf{a}$. The probed singular values then take the form:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{\Sigma}} = \mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T\mathbf{a}. \tag{8}$$

To construct energy functions, we can apply the anisotropically filtered singular values.

Algorithm 1 Anisotropic smoothed particle hydrodynamics solver

```

1: for all particles  $i$  do
2:   search all neighbor particles  $j$ 
3: end for
4: while simulation is running do
5:   procedure ADVECTION STEP
6:     for all particles  $i$  do
7:       deformation gradient  $\mathbf{F}_i$  (Eqn. 4)
8:       isotropic energy function
        $\Psi_{iso,i}$  (Tab. 1)
9:       isotropic PK1 tensor  $\mathbf{P}_{iso,i}$  (Tab. 1)
10:      anisotropic energy and its
       according PK1  $\mathbf{P}_{ani,i}$  (Eqn. 9, 12)
11:      elastic force  $\mathbf{f}_i^{ela}$  (Eqn. 17)
12:      add gravity as advection force
        $\mathbf{f}_i^{adv} = \mathbf{f}_i^{ela} + \mathbf{f}_i^{gra}$ 
13:      update advection velocity
        $\mathbf{v}_i^{adv} = \mathbf{v}_i(t) + \mathbf{f}_i^{adv} \Delta t$ 
14:     end for
15:   end procedure
16:   procedure INCOMPRESSIBLE SOLVER
17:     while  $\mathbf{v}_i^{adv}$  is compressible do
18:       for all particles  $i$  do
19:         update advection velocity
          $\mathbf{v}_i^{adv} = \text{imcomp-solver}(\mathbf{v}_i^{adv})$ 
20:       end for
21:     end while
22:   for all particles  $i$  do
23:     update velocity and position
      $\mathbf{v}_i = \mathbf{v}_i^{adv}$ ,  $\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{x}_i(t) + \mathbf{v}_i \Delta t$ 
24:   end for
25:   end procedure
26:   procedure DIVERGENCE-FREE SOLVER
27:     while  $\mathbf{v}_i$  is not divergence-free do
28:       update velocity field
        $\mathbf{v}_i = \text{div-free-solver}(\mathbf{v}_i)$ 
29:     end while
30:   end procedure
31: end while

```

However, to avoid the actual need for computing SVD, I_5^{ext} is employed in [25]. In I_5^{ext} , the rotation part is canceled out, similar to I_1 . In [18], Kim and Eberle further pointed out that the sum of the weighted squares of eigenvalues fails to capture negativity, resulting in an inability to effectively capture the inversion of elements. To address this issue, they proposed sign-preserving invariant I_4^{ext} as a substitute.

Figure 5: Elastic cuboid squashing experiments utilizing both isotropic and a combination of isotropic and anisotropic energies, with a Young’s modulus of $E = 5 \times 10^4$ for all cases. The figure employs color-coding to represent the forces applied on the particles, with more intense colors indicating a higher degree of resistance. The Neo-Hookean energy is used.

4.1 Anisotropic functions

In this paper, we employ the inversion-safe form of the anisotropic energy function proposed in [17], given by:

$$\Psi_{ani} = \frac{\mu}{2} \left(\sqrt{I_5^{ext}} + \text{sgn}(I_4^{ext}) \right)^2, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{ani} = \mu \left(1 - \frac{\text{sgn}(I_4^{ext})}{\sqrt{I_5^{ext}}} \right) \mathbf{F}\mathbf{A}, \quad (10)$$

where sgn denotes the signum function as:

$$\text{sgn}(x) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } x < 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } x > 0 \end{cases}. \quad (11)$$

The signum function in Equation 9 ensures that the value of Ψ_{ani} reaches its minimum at the undeformed state and gradually increases for both compression and stretching. This formulation successfully avoids the bimodal minimum issue that occurs in previous anisotropic methods, where another minimum appears in the negative singular value state.

To model muscle contraction and relaxation, we introduce two additional variables into Equation 9 to flexibly adjust the effect of anisotropic

Figure 6: Elastic cuboid stretching experiments utilizing both isotropic and a combination of isotropic and anisotropic energies, with a Young's modulus of $E = 5 \times 10^4$ for all cases. The figure employs color-coding to represent the forces applied on the particles, with more intense colors indicating a higher degree of resistance. The Neo-Hookean energy is used.

energy:

$$\Psi_{ani}^{mus} = c_a \left(\sqrt{I_5^{ext}} + c_l \operatorname{sgn}(I_4^{ext}) \right)^2, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{ani}^{mus} = 2c_a \left(1 - c_l \frac{\operatorname{sgn}(I_4^{ext})}{\sqrt{I_5^{ext}}} \right) \mathbf{FA}, \quad (13)$$

where c_a is the activation coefficient, which describes the force of contraction, and c_l is the length coefficient, which determines how much the muscle should shrink. As can be seen from Equation 9, the graph of this energy function is a quadratic curve. The coefficient c_a controls the steepness of the curve, while c_l determines the value of I_4^{ext} at which the curve reaches its minimum point.

Figure 7: An elastic pad falls onto a tetrahedral pyramid. The figure employs color-coding to represent the forces applied on the particles. In the first row of isotropic elasticity experiments, the pad is subjected to uniform force in the horizontal direction. In the second row of anisotropic experiments, the force on the pad exhibits directionality, causing significant bending in only one direction. The anisotropy direction is along the y axis of the top view.

5 Force computation

5.1 Elastic force

After obtaining both isotropic and anisotropic energies Ψ_{iso} and Ψ_{ani} , as well as the resulting PK1 stress tensors \mathbf{P}_{iso} and \mathbf{P}_{ani} , we can compute the final stress tensor as:

$$\mathbf{P}_{fin} = \mathbf{P}_{iso} + \mathbf{P}_{ani}. \quad (14)$$

To ultimately derive the force from the stress tensor as $\mathbf{f} = V \nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}$, while preserving the conservation of momentum between particles, we utilize the SPH computation form in [5] to ensure that the elastic forces between two particles are equivalent. The elastic force from particle j to the neighboring particle i , according to Equation 2, is:

$$\mathbf{f}_{j \rightarrow i}^{ela} = V_i V_j \mathbf{P}_i \nabla_i W_{\vec{ij}}. \quad (15)$$

We should also note that particle i exerts forces on j as:

$$\mathbf{f}_{i \rightarrow j}^{ela} = V_i V_j \mathbf{P}_j \nabla_j W_{\vec{ji}}. \quad (16)$$

To conserve the momentum for the entire system, the elastic force experienced by i takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}_i^{ela} &= \sum_j \mathbf{f}_{j \rightarrow i}^{ela} - \sum_j \mathbf{f}_{i \rightarrow j}^{ela} \\ &= \sum_j V_i V_j (\mathbf{P}_i \nabla_i W_{ij} - \mathbf{P}_j \nabla_j W_{ji}) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

5.2 Divergence-free incompressibility

In order to apply the strong incompressibility into the elastic object, we incorporate the elastic simulation with divergence-free constraint from [7]. The elastic force acts as a part of the advection procedure during the whole advection-projection scheme. As is shown in Algorithm 1, the elastic force computation corresponds to the line 7-11 of the advection step procedure. Then combined with the force from gravity (if needed), we can get the advection velocity in line 13.

Two iterative solvers from [7] take place after the advection step. The first incompressible solver from line 16-25 updates both velocity and position for each particle to arrive at incompressible state at the next time step. The divergence-free solver (line 26-30) then further adjust the velocity field at the next time step to a divergence-free state to ensure a more robust simulation condition.

6 Experiments

In this section we carry out several sets of experiments demonstrating the efficacy and capability of the proposed particle-based anisotropic model. We color-coded several experiments (Figures 3,4,5,6,7) to visualize the elastic force applied onto the particle. We use deeper colors to represent stronger forces. The elastic coupling method in [37] is applied to handle the object coupling.

6.1 Anisotropic elasticity

Following the experiments in Figures 3,4, We validated the anisotropic elasticity energy based on the Neo-Hookean model, setting the anisotropy direction as $\mathbf{a} = [1, 0, 0]^T$. The results are presented from three distinct perspec-

tives, demonstrating that elastomers exhibit a stiffer effect in the anisotropy direction. Figure 5 and Figure 6 illustrate that, under isotropic elasticity, the material compresses uniformly in all directions, whereas, for anisotropic elasticity, the material expands more significantly in the direction perpendicular to the anisotropy direction.

6.2 Cone impact

To demonstrate how anisotropic material responds to sudden impacts differently from isotropic one, we conduct the experiment illustrating the behavior of an elastic object falling onto a pyramid under both isotropic and anisotropic conditions.

In the top view, we removed the upper particles to more effectively observe the elastic forces acting on the internal particles. As depicted in Figure 7, the internal forces within the elastic object are uniform under isotropic conditions. The vivid colors indicate that particles experience a greater elastic force in the anisotropic direction.

Without the incompressible solver

With the incompressible solver

Figure 8: Elastic cuboid squashing experiments with a Young's modulus of $E = 5 \times 10^4$ for all cases, conducted under various Poisson's ratios. In the first row, all experiments are simulated without the divergence-free SPH constraint. In the second row, the SPH constraint is applied to all cases.

6.3 Incompressibility from implicit SPH

We compared the squashing effect with and without the incompressible solver, varying Poisson's ratio from 0.2 to 0.49. As shown in Fig-

Figure 9: Comparison of compressibility with or without the SPH incompressible solver in elasticity compression experiments in Figure 8. The left graph displays the statistical results from all experiments with various Poisson’s ratios. The right graph presents a zoomed view of the cases involving the SPH incompressible solver. The Young’s modulus is $E = 5 \times 10^4$ for all cases, except for one case with $E = 5 \times 10^5$, labeled on the right side.

Figure 10: Muscle contraction and relaxation drive bone movement. The activation length is set to $c_l = 0.4$ in this experiment. The red color indicates the level of muscle activation, with white representing no activation.

ure 8, without an incompressible solver, the degree of compression is influenced by the Poisson’s ratio. A larger Poisson’s ratio results in smaller elastic compressibility and a higher degree of extrusion. When the implicit incompressible constraint is incorporated into the simulation, even a Poisson’s ratio significantly less than 0.5 can maintain a stable incompressible state.

We further analyzed the overall compression ratio for this experiment in Figure 9. During the squashing of the elastic object, when Poisson’s ratio is constant, changing Young’s modulus does not affect compressibility when the incompressible constraint is applied. As illustrated on the right of Figure 9, with an incompressible solver, the compression ratio fluctuates within a very narrow range.

Another interesting observation from the black group of lines is that maintaining the Young’s modulus while changing the Poisson’s ratio does not alter the compressible state. How-

ever, introducing additional anisotropic constraints may potentially make the elastic object more compressible, emphasizing the importance of maintaining the incompressibility of elastic elements.

6.4 Muscle simulation of the bicep and the crawling snake

To explore the versatility of our method for animation production and special effects, we simulated the movements of a human bicep and a crawling snake separately.

We simulated the impact of muscle contraction and relaxation on bone movement (Figure 10). First, we gradually increased the activation factor (indicated by color intensity), causing the muscle to contract and lift the bone. Then, the activation coefficient decreased, leading the muscle to relax and the bone to extend again. The experiment demonstrated that our method can realistically simulate muscle motion.

In another experiment, we accurately simu-

lated the crawling motion of a snake on the ground by controlling the contraction and expansion of two muscles in the snake's head. This generated a twisting motion of the snake's body, resulting in forward movement. The alternating control of the muscles faithfully replicated the movement of a real snake, providing a realistic depiction of the scenario.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented a particle-based smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) framework for simulating hyperelastic materials with anisotropic stiffness models. Our approach combines an implicit divergence-free SPH solver with particle-based deformation gradient computation and various elastic energy functions to achieve incompressible elastic simulations. By incorporating anisotropic energy functions constructed from the extrapolation of Cauchy-Green invariants and integrating activation and contraction coefficients, our method effectively represents elastic objects with varying mechanical properties across different directions and can be employed to mimic muscle contractions.

Our framework addresses the current gap in anisotropic elastic simulation studies for particle-based techniques and offers a more robust and versatile solution compared to traditional mesh-based methods. The experiments conducted in this study demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in providing realistic simulations for a wide range of animal and human body movements, highlighting its potential for diverse applications in computer graphics, biomechanics, and material science.

However, our method does have certain limitations. Specifically, it struggles with the simulation of extreme squeezing and stretching in highly rigid elastic bodies. Although the combination of Neo-Hookean energy functions and divergence-free SPH computation provides a degree of stability, our method is unable to handle arbitrary deformation in these cases. The particle system becomes unstable and may even explode when particles are too far apart from each other under high Young's modulus conditions. This issue arises from the fixed initial relative

positions and neighbor relationships between SPH particles, which generate numerical instability when particles are too distant from one another, particularly when the Young's modulus is high. Moving forward, we plan to explore techniques to implicitly manage extremely rigid elastic solids and enhance the stability of our method, further expanding its applicability to an even broader range of simulations.

In future work, we intend to explore the integration of our particle-based framework with other simulation techniques to create more complex and detailed scenes. Furthermore, we aim to optimize our method for large-scale simulations and real-time applications. We plan to investigate the application of our approach to a broader range of anisotropic materials, enabling more accurate and realistic simulations across various domains.

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Figure 11: Simulating snake crawling by controlling the contraction of left and right head muscles. The red particles represent activated and shrinking muscle segments.

Figure 12: Top view of snake crawling simulation in Figure 11.

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